

Ternary Complexes of Copper(II), Zinc(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) with Nitrilotriacetic Acid and Substituted Salicylic Acids

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Biligand complex forming systems of the type : $M\text{-NTA-L}$ [$M=\text{Cu(II), Zn(II), Ni(II)}$ and Co(II) ions ; NTA=nitrilotriacetic acid ; L=5-nitrosalicylic acid (NSA) and 5-chlorosalicylic acid (CSA)] have been investigated potentiometrically [25°, $\mu=0.1M$ (NaClO_4), medium—50% v/v aqueous-ethanol]. Under identical conditions, the binary complexes of NSA and CSA have also been examined. The logarithms of the mixed ligand formation constants of complexes in $M\text{-NTA-NSA}$ systems, $\log K_{M,NTA,NSA}^M$ are 5.46, 4.28, 4.23 and 3.89 respectively. The logarithms of the first step formation constants of binary $M\text{-NSA}$ complexes $\log K_1$ are 9.81, 7.22, 6.53 and 6.18 respectively. Only Cu(II) and Zn(II) complexes could be studied with CSA and the values of $\log K_{M,NTA,CSA}^M$ and $\log K_1$ are 5.46, 4.49 ; and 8.77, 7.26 respectively. The second step formation constants could be obtained only in the case of Cu-NSA and Cu-CSA systems, the values of $\log K_2$ being 7.11 and 6.46 respectively.

BINARY complexes of 5-nitrosalicylic acid¹⁻⁶ (NSA) and 5-chlorosalicylic acid⁸ (CSA) with a number of metal ions have been reported in literature. The work described here deals with the investigation of ternary complexing systems of the type : $M\text{-NTA-L}$ [$M=\text{Cu(II), Zn(II), Ni(II)}$ and Co(II) ; NTA=nitrilotriacetic acid and L=NSA and CSA] involving NTA as a primary and L as secondary ligands at 25° and at an ionic strength of 0.1 M (NaClO_4) in 50% v/v aqueous-ethanol medium adopting Irving and Rossotti pH-titration technique⁷ as modified by Chidambaram and Bhattacharya⁸. Studies on the binary complexes of the secondary ligands under identical conditions have also been examined. Though such studies with NSA in aqueous medium have already been reported¹⁻⁶, no work appears to be on record on CSA with the ions studied here.

Experimental

Solutions and related materials :

Solutions of copper (II), zinc (II), nickel (II) and cobalt (II) perchlorates were prepared and standardized⁹. Suitable volumes of these solutions were separately diluted and perchloric acid added if necessary to obtain 0.01 M metal perchlorate in 0.02 M perchloric acid. A stock solution of sodium perchlorate (1.0 M) was prepared and standardized¹⁰.

Stock solutions of CO_2 -free sodium hydroxide (0.098 M) and perchloric acid (0.02 M) were

prepared and used after standardization. Solutions of the chelating agents (0.005 M) viz. nitrilotriacetic acid (in water) ; 5-nitrosalicylic acid (in ethanol) and 5-chlorosalicylic acid (in ethanol) were prepared by direct weighing.

All the reagents used were of analytical grade.

Procedure :

Measurements were carried out using Leeds and Northrup pH-meter with a glass-calomel electrode assembly at 25°. The medium was 50% v/v aqueous ethanol and ionic strength 0.1 M (NaClO_4).

(a) $M\text{-L}$ Systems :

Three titration mixtures (total volume 50.0 ml), viz. (A) acid, (B) ligand, and (C) chelate were prepared¹¹. The concentrations were : $N^0=0.098 M$; $E^0=0.002 M$; $\text{TC}_x^0=0.001 M$; and $\text{TC}_M=0.0002 M$ (symbols having usual meanings⁷). Mixtures A, B and C were individually titrated against standard alkali and thus three titration curves A, B and C were obtained for each system. For illustration titration curves of only $M\text{-CSA}$ systems (fig. 1) are being given here.

(b) $M\text{-NTA-L}$ systems :

Mixtures containing (D) 5.0 ml perchloric acid (0.02 M)+5.0 ml sodium perchlorate (1.0 M)+10.0 ml NTA (0.005 M)+5.0 ml water+25.0 ml ethanol ; (E) 5.0 ml metal perchlorate (0.01 M in 0.02 M perchloric acid)+5.0 ml sodium perchlorate (1.0 M)+10.0 ml NTA (0.005 M)+5.0 ml water+25.0 ml

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ethanol; (F) 5.0 ml perchloric acid (0.02 M)+7.5 ml perchloric acid (0.02 M) (to account for the protons liberated as a result of complexations of NTA with

all the M-L systems investigated, precipitation occurred even before the stage of 1 : 1 or 1 : 2 [only in case of Cu(II)] complexation was complete, and no

Fig. 1 Titration curves M-CSA systems -O-O-acid (A); -x-x-CSA (B); -O-O-Cu(II)-CSA.-●-●-Zn(II)-CSA

Fig. 2 Titration curves Cu(II)-NTA-NSA system ●-●-NTA (D); -O-O-Cu(II)-NTA (E); -x-x-NSA (F); -●-●-Cu(II)-NTA-NSA (G)

metal ions)+5.0 ml sodium perchlorate (1.0 M)+10.0 ml NSA or CSA (0.005 M)+7.5 ml water+15.0 ml ethanol and (G) 5.0 ml metal perchlorate (0.01 M in 0.02 M perchloric acid)+5.0 ml sodium perchlorate (1.0 M)+10.0 ml NTA (0.005 M)+10.0 ml NSA or CSA (0.005 M)+5.0 ml water+15.0 ml ethanol were prepared. The excess acidity in mixtures F and G as compared to A was taken into account in the calculations. The mixtures were separately titrated against standard alkali, whereby titration curves D, E, F and G in each of the systems were obtained. Titration curves of only Cu(II)-NTA-NSA system are being given here (Fig. 2).

Calculations

M-L Systems :

From the titration curves A, B, and C (curve C designated by the respective metal ions in fig. 1), the parameters \bar{n}_A , average number of protons associated with the ligand L, \bar{n} , average number of ligand molecules attached per metal ion and pL , free ligand exponent were calculated using the formulae of Irving and Rossotti⁷, and the formation constants corresponding to the proton-ligand metal-ligand systems obtained by average value method are recorded in Table 1.

The absence of polynuclear species etc. was confirmed by using several concentrations of the reactants and the results obtained were identical. In

studies beyond this stage were possible. Hence, the hydroxospecies likely to be formed after this stage could not be studied.

TABLE-1 STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY (M-L) AND TERNARY (M-NTA-L) CHELATES IN 50% v/v AQUEOUS-ETHANOL MEDIUM (25°, $\mu=0.1$)

Cation	log K_1	log K_2	log $K_{M,NTA}^{M,NTA,L}$
(a) Secondary ligand - NSA			
H ⁺	11.01	2.86	—
Cu(II)	9.81	7.11	5.46
Zn(II)	7.22	—	4.28
Ni(II)	6.53	—	4.23
Co(II)	6.18	—	3.89
(b) Secondary ligand - CSA			
H ⁺	11.52	3.19	—
Cu(II)	8.77	6.49	5.46
Zn(II)	7.26	—	4.49

M-NTA-L systems :

Complete formation of (M. NTA)⁻ complex species occurs at $pH \approx 4$, which remain stable at higher pH values [analyses of curves A (fig. 1), D and E (fig. 2)]. The mixed ligand titration curve G departs from the secondary ligand titration curve F, after complete formation of (M.NTA)⁻ species in all the systems. It may thus be assumed that the secondary ligand NSA or CSA would combine with (M. NTA)⁻ species in ternary systems similarly as it does with $[M.(H_2O)_n]^{2+}$ in the binary systems.

The horizontal distance between the curves G and F were used for the calculation of \bar{n}_{mix} , the average number of NSA or CSA molecules attached per $(M.NTA)^-$ ions using the equation :

$$\bar{n}_{mix} = \frac{(v^G - v^F)(N^o + E^o)}{(V^o + V)\bar{n}_A TC_{M,NTA^o}} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where v^G and v^F are the volumes of alkali consumed to reach the same pH-values in the curves G and F of the mixed ligand systems. TC_{M,NTA^o} is the concentration of $(M.NTA)^-$ complex which is equivalent to the initial metal ion concentration. All other symbols have their usual meanings⁷. \bar{n}_A values at different pH were available from the binary complexing systems. From the values of \bar{n}_{mix} so obtained, free ligand exponent, pL_{mix} were calculated using the equation :

$$pL_{mix} = \log_{10} \left[\frac{\sum_{n=0}^j \beta_n^H \left(\frac{1}{\text{anti log } B} \right)^n}{(TC_{L^o} - \bar{n}_{mix} \cdot TC_{M,NTA^o}) \cdot \frac{V^o + V}{V^o}} \right] \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

Formation curves corresponding to various mixed ligand systems were obtained by plotting \bar{n}_{mix} vs pL_{mix} (figs. omitted) and the corresponding formation constants obtained by average value method are recorded in table 1.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand systems :

The formation curves of the ligands NSA or CSA (figs. not shown) exhibit a wave like shape suggesting two distinct steps corresponding to the protonation of carboxylate group and the phenolic oxygen of the ligands.

It is well known that the presence of electron withdrawing nitro group in phenols or benzoic acid increases their acidity. Similarly chloro group, in general, exerts an electron withdrawing inductive effect, but also an electron donating mesomeric effect, when located at *ortho*- or *para* positions to either of them. Further the inductive effect is more pronounced with nitro group than the chloro group¹². The influence of the location of nitro group in NSA and chloro group in CSA thus results in the protonation constants of NSA being less than those of CSA (Table 1).

Binary systems :

In the M-L binary systems Cu(II) forms both 1:1 and 1:2 complexes, while other ions form only 1:1 (1:2 complex species could not be examined as explained). The formation of complexes, in systems Ni(II)-CSA and Co(II)-CSA,

however, seemed to be doubtful as the \bar{n} values were appreciably low to provide any reliable value of stability constants, and hence these systems have not been pursued.

The stabilities of the metal complexes (Table 1) follow the trend :

which is in conformity with the Irving-Williams order¹³. Also, values of $\log K_1$ (K_1 =first step formation constant in M-L systems) for various complexes other than that of copper (II) are fairly close to each other. The stabilities of copper (II) complexes are usually higher than could be expected from ionic radius or electro-negativity considerations¹⁴. This additional stability of copper(II) complexes may be attributed to the unique electronic configuration (d^9) of Cu(II) ion which is capable of additional stabilization due to Jahn-Teller distortion.

The Irving-Williams order runs roughly parallel to the second ionization potential of the elements which provides information on the affinity of the central atom to accept electrons from the ligands in covalent bond formation. The $\log K_1$ values for the metal complexes were thus plotted against the respective second ionization potentials and a straight line was obtained (fig. 3). The point corresponding to Ni(II), however, does not fall on the line and is below it, showing that nickel(II) complexes possessed a low degree of stability with the ligand (NSA).

Fig. 3 $\log K_{M,NTA,NSA}^{M,NTA}$ vs second ionization potential (a); $\log K_{M,NTA,NSA}^{M,NTA}$ vs $\log K_1$ (b); $\log K_1$ vs second ionization potential (c).

Ternary Systems :

It is observed that the values of $\log K_{M,NTA,L}^{M,NTA}$

($K_{M,NTA,L}^{M,NTA}$ = stoichiometric mixed ligand complex

formation constant in M-NTA-L systems) is less than $\log K_1$ and even less than $\log K_2$ (K_1 and K_2 are the step formation constants of the binary complexes of the secondary ligands). This behaviour can be explained on the basis of coulombic interactions between various ligand anion species present. In the mixed ligand complex formation there is repulsion between two negative charges from the secondary ligand anion and three negative charges from the NTA anions. The extent of this repulsion would obviously be more than that encountered between two negative charges each from the two secondary ligand anions, in the formation of ML_2

species, ultimately resulting in $\log K_{M.NTA} < \log K_2$.

No such interaction is encountered in the formation of ML species. The value of $\log K_1$ being greater than $\log K_2$ are well established, which then finally justifies the order $\log K_1 > \log K_2 > \log K_{M.NTA.L}$

In all the ternary systems studied, the order of stability of mixed ligand complexes with respect to the metal ions was found to be

which is the same as in corresponding binary M-L systems.

The plot of $\log K_{M.NTA} \text{ vs } \log K_1$ (fig. 3) gives

a straight line indicating that the process of association of L with $(M.NTA)^-$ species in the ternary

systems follows, in general, the same pattern as that during the association of L with $[M(H_2O)_n]^{2+}$ in the corresponding binary complexing systems.

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